

POSSIBILITIES OF THE INTERACTIVE ENCOURAGEMENT METHOD IN INCREASING THE VOCABULARY OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article reviews the works of pedagogic-psychologists who conducted scientific research on various psychological, behavioral and educational theories, the theoretical foundations of motivational methods in education. Some key theoretical perspectives that help to understand the role of motivation in education are highlighted. Instructions are provided on the use of interactive motivational methods that increase the effectiveness of primary education, which is the main link of education, and provide interdisciplinary integration.*

Keywords: *motivation, motivation, education, training, method, integration, interactive method, behavior, reward, punishment.*

Educating a person to the level of a well-rounded person is a complex process, and mature people of society have been involved in this activity since ancient times. This situation means that the organization and content of the education of the young generation is important in determining not only the development of the individual, but also the development of the society. These experiences are of great importance in the creative application of teaching laws and principles used in teaching forms, in the practical implementation of ideas, theories, and laws related to scientific knowledge.

Today, improving the primary education process, which is one of the main foundations of the education system, is defined as an important task of modern pedagogy. During the Third Renaissance, which is being established in Uzbekistan, the following are defined as the main tasks of primary education:

- development of analytical and creative thinking abilities of elementary school students;
- improvement of primary education based on advanced foreign experiences;
- achieving the effectiveness of primary education. [1]

In performing these tasks, pedagogues and educators are required to have strong knowledge, high pedagogical skills, creativity and the ability to achieve educational efficiency. In order to achieve the effectiveness of education, it is important that the teaching process is meaningful, high-quality and certainly interesting. To make students interested in learning is done by encouraging them. A teacher-pedagogue should be able to use interactive ways to motivate students based on the subject of study, the topic of the lesson, the spirit of the class team and his pedagogical capabilities.

The concept of motivation is broad, and it has forms such as approval, praise, reward, giving a commendation, thanking, awarding in front of the class group, giving compensation and rewarding with other rewards. The world's leading pedagogic scientists conducted scientific research on the pedagogical and psychological possibilities of rewarding and punishing students. Abu Nasr Farabi, Alisher Navoi, Abu Rayhan Beruni from Eastern thinkers and D.S. from world

pedagogic scientists. Shedrin, A.S. Makarenko, K.D. Ushinsky, A.Sh. Amonashvili, L. Yu. Gordin, B. F. Skinner, Desi, Ryan, Bandura, Locke, and Latham conducted research on motivation and punishment methods.

Encouragement is a positive assessment of the child's behavior, performing a stimulating function in education. Its stimulating role is determined by public recognition of the course of action chosen and implemented by the student.[2]

Abu Nasr Farabi pays attention to two aspects of a person's spiritual life: the mind of intelligence and morality. Therefore, in his opinion, education should be focused on intellectual and moral maturity. In the process of education and training, theoretical knowledge and practical actions, usual skills and activities are combined, and maturity occurs depending on the degree of this combination. Farabi writes about the methods of education as follows: the first method: with the help of satisfying, inviting, inspiring words, habits are formed and skills are created, enthusiasm in a person, aspiration for a profession is turned into action. The second way: the way of coercion. This method is mandatory training of the trainees.[3]

Teaching the student is carried out through inspiring words that increase his internal motivation and encourage him to perform activities. A student who receives praise and applause increases his interest in learning.

The theoretical foundations of motivational methods in education are based on various psychological, behavioral and educational theories. There are some key theoretical perspectives that help us understand the role of motivation in learning:

Behavioral Economics: Behavioral economics studies how individuals make decisions and respond to incentives. Concepts such as reinforcement, reward and punishment play an important role in the formation of behavior. How rewards and consequences influence students' choices, actions and participation in the learning process through the lens of behavioral economics. can be seen by understanding the mystery.

Operant conditioning theory (B. F. Skinner): Skinner's operant conditioning theory emphasizes the role of consequences in shaping behavior. Positive reinforcement strengthens a behavior, while negative reinforcement or punishment weakens it.

According to Skinner's model, learning occurs when an ongoing operant comes under the control of environmental reinforcement. Initially, the operant can be formed by increasing the approximation to the desired operant symbol. The likelihood of occurrence of the operant increases when an event that reinforces the processed operant is observed. Skinner did not support the use of punishment. His research showed that punishment is an ineffective method of controlling behavior, which usually leads to short-term changes in behavior, but as a result, the subject mainly avoids the behavior that caused the punishment. instead, it tries to avoid the punishing stimulus.[4] In educational applications, rewards such as rewards for academic achievement or consequences for incomplete assignments follow the principles of operant conditioning to encourage desired behaviors in educational settings.

The practice of operant conditioning is widely used in many areas, including education and psychology. For example, a classroom teacher asks students questions and students get a good grade for correct answers, or students get a bad grade for making a mistake in an exercise. This method ensures learning and the structure of critical punishments during learning.

Self-determination theory (Desi and Ryan): Self-determination theory motivates individuals with a need for autonomy, agency, and relatedness. Internal motivation is more stable

and effective than external motivation. According to their theory, the effectiveness of the activity depends on how strong the internal motivation is in a person. But in order for them to really exist and manifest, favorable conditions must be created for them. Humanistic psychologists talked more about this, and Deci and Ryan repeated after them, if you know the need for development, if you create favorable conditions for it, then internal motivation will increase and manifest itself more and more in a person. If the external conditions are unfavorable, we will see that the internal motivation starts to weaken and the person will have to use the carrot and stick method to do something. What are the external conditions that can create favorable conditions for internal motivation or, on the contrary, destroy this internal motivation, create an ineffective person? First, the need for skills must be met. When the need for competence is satisfied, a person experiences a sense of competence. This is the feeling that the need is properly satisfied.[5]

In the educational process, incentives should be designed to support intrinsic motivation by providing choice, skill enhancement, and fostering positive relationships between students and the learning environment.

Cognitive appraisal theory (Deci): This theory expands on self-determination theory and focuses on how external factors, such as rewards, influence intrinsic motivation. It distinguishes between control and informational aspects of rewards. Encouragement that enhances the learner's sense of competence and autonomy can positively influence intrinsic motivation, while excessive control can undermine it.

Deci conducted certain experiments that show that a monetary reward can be perceived by an individual as a form of control. This reward does not improve motivation, but reduces it and causes changes for the worse. Deci has proven that it is not necessary to use some external factors to increase activity. He believed that this can be helped by the self-strengthening that comes from the subject himself.

Goal Setting Theory (Locke and Latham): Goal setting theory emphasizes the importance of setting clear and challenging goals to increase motivation and performance. Feedback and encouragement can contribute to goal achievement. Methods of encouragement include providing clear goals, providing rewards for goal achievement, and providing constructive feedback to support students in achieving their academic goals. may be consistent with the principles of goal setting.

Locke and Latham's goal setting theory is widely used in corporate financial organizations, educational systems, and learning. It shows the importance of people in mastering and achieving goals. A lot of motivation is created to see the value of goals, to achieve them and to implement them. This theory creates the concept of clearly defining goals in practice and showing the way to achieve them.

Social cognitive theory (Bandura): social cognitive theory emphasizes the role of observational learning, self-regulation, and the interaction between personal, behavioral, and environmental factors. Positive motivation methods can be designed to model behavior, promote self-regulation, and create a supportive learning environment that encourages students to take an active role in their learning.

Expectancy-Value Theory (Eccles and Wigfield): This theory examines how individuals make choices based on their expectations of success and the perceived value of a task. Motivation is influenced by the belief that action will lead to success and the importance attached to the task.

Motivational techniques can be designed to raise students' expectations of success and emphasize the importance and relevance of the learning tasks they are performing.

Understanding and integrating these theoretical frameworks can help educators and policy makers develop effective motivational strategies that promote positive learning outcomes and contribute to the overall success of Socratic questions in educational settings.

Children living in the age of innovation are now being educated in a system where traditional approaches to education are less effective than they should be. Developing the intelligence of elementary school students through the use of interactive stimulation at school is a modern and effective way to develop their strong intellectual abilities and critical thinking. The following interactive method of stimulation serves to ensure students' activity in the course of the lesson, to increase vocabulary, and to strengthen their knowledge of foreign language learning. "Eureka!" method.

Students are divided into 3 groups. For each group, words belonging to a foreign language are selected separately in an envelope, and the letters of the words are written on the cards. Which word to choose depends on the subject being studied. The number of letters in the word should be equal. Words can be terms and concepts related to this science.

Pupils get the letters of their group by their activity during the lesson, complete and correct completion of homework and resourcefulness. At the end of the lesson, they combine the letters of each group to form their own word and paint the letters in any color. The students who fulfill the condition first will be declared the winner. The resulting words are translated by the teacher, and the students write down new words in their dictionary notebooks.

Words to use:

№	Subject name	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3
1	Mathematics	Square	Circle	Sphere
2	Mother tongue	Talk	Word	Text
3	Reading literacy	Story	Novel	Poems
4	Natural science	Rain	Snow	Hail

Incentives and punishments are used side by side. In this method, as a punishment, the last letter obtained from the groups that broke the rules of the lesson and could not maintain discipline is taken away.

This method is a motivating factor for ensuring interdisciplinary integration, increasing students' internal motivation to learn, enriching didactic tools in education, increasing educational efficiency, developing students' cognitive activities, and increasing foreign language skills. Also, students will acquire skills such as working together, being disciplined and responsible, and self-control.

Interactive stimulation forces students to directly participate in the learning process, which makes it different. Instead of passively viewing information, students actively interact with it. It encourages intellectual development, because with this approach, children have the ability to analyze and critically evaluate information, solve problems creatively, and work as a team.

In general, interactive stimulation is a powerful tool used by teachers to help develop the intelligence of young students. By engaging students in interesting and practical aspects of education, it serves to create a basis for them to achieve success during learning.

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